
The Ancient Indian Knowledge System-Ayurveda as Beacon of Modern Health and Medicine

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Abstract Ayurveda, a holistic system of medicine derived from the Sanskrit word Ayur- life and Veda – Knowledge, means knowledge of life. The ancient Indian Knowledge system are related to modern health and medicine. For the formulation of modern indigenous system of medicine in various countries the oldest known remedies by medicinal plants have significant role. Ayurveda offers a complete system to live a long healthy life. Ayurveda is considered to be originated in India more than 5000 years ago and is rooted to Atharvaveda. According to WHO (1948), Health is- ‘a state of complete physical, mental, and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity’. So this is the holistic approach which is already aimed in Ayurveda to promote health and wellbeing by balancing between mind, body and spirit. Charaka--Samhita, Sushruta-Samhita and Astanga-Hridaya are the primary texts of Ayurveda which describes the etymology, symptomology and therapeutics for a wide range of diseases as well as diet, hygiene, Pathology, Diagnosis, Anatomy, Pharmaceutics, Toxicology, Surgery, Medicinal plants, and medical education. In 21st century in view to fulfilling the goals of sustainable development established by the United Nations members, ancient Indian Knowledge system will be the pathway for transforming India to Viksit Bharat and it will create a new education system globally which is rooted in India. We could say Ayurveda is the stepping stone to “ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages”. Modern medicine which is based on scientific and evidence based practices and technology could be guided by Ayurveda through holistic health, personalized care and lifestyle and dietary adjustments. In this article the importance and the relevance of Ayurveda with modern medicine to unlock Holistic health will be reviewed.

Keywords: Ayurveda, Holistic health, Sustainable Development, Modern medicine, Viksit- Bharat

Introduction

Ayurveda is a holistic system of medicine which emphasizes the balance between mind, body, spirit and environment. The NEP 2020 emphasizes on inclusion of Indian

Knowledge System in our education system which aims to explore and recapitulate India’s rich traditional knowledge like Ayurveda, Yoga, Mathematics, Philosophy, Technology, Ethics and more among students. India has a rich heritage of knowledge and culture, which is evident in its collection of ancient manuscripts, written in different languages, Shastras, oral traditions. Ayurveda, the knowledge of life or the science of life is the upa-veda of Atharvaveda, one among four Vedas. Different classical texts in Ayurveda are Samhitas, which serve as the source of Indian traditional system of medicine which are related to health and diseases. Charaka Samhita,

Sushruta Samhita and Ashtanga-Hridaya are the three main texts of Ayurveda. Acharya Charaka who was the one of the principal contributors to Ayurveda edited Charaka Samhita.

The Samhita contains theoretical knowledge which focuses on healing the body, mind and soul of a patient called Kaya Chikitsa through minimum invasive manner. Charaka Samhita is written in Sanskrit language and deals with internal and external application of medicine. It is composed of 9295 sutras and 120 adhyayas (Badge *et.al.*,2013). Sushruta Samhita which is named after an ancient surgeon Shuruta is divided into six sthana, namely Sutra Sthana, Nidana Sthana, Shareer Sthana, Chikitsa sthana, Kalpa sthana, Uttara tantra. It describes many basic principles related to surgery, surgical techniques, anatomy, embryology, disease diagnosis and treatments. One ancient school of thought within Ayurveda – Dhanvantari Sampradaya is known for surgery, gifted to us by Shushruta, who is the main disciple of this Sampradaya. Shushruta is regarded as the father of plastic surgery or cosmetic surgery (kembhavi S.A *et.al.*,2022).

The first International Congress on Ayurveda which was held in March 2009 in Milan, Italy established a bridge between Western and Indian scientific, philosophical, biomedical thinking. The main focus of the speakers of this congress was in connecting living beings with environment which automatically shape Nature. This concept is already there in Ayurveda where the interdependence or interconnectedness is the core principle and defines “the meaning of life.” Professor Alex Hankey, Department of Yoga and Physical Science, Bangalore, India enlightened on achieving “perfect health” by gaining insight into the nature in “The Ayurvedic concepts of Perfect Health”. Dr. Rama Jaysundar, AIIMS, New Delhi, India related some concepts of quantum physics with Ayurveda as Ayurveda tells about the interconnectedness of human body within as well as outside. In the same congress Dr. Gianluigi Marini, Director, Oncology, Saint Anna Hospital, Switzerland in “A New Paradigm for Cancer: From the Extreme Expression of organic Disease to the outstanding Example of Functional pathogenesis of Disease” suggested that health and diseases are derived from structured information interconnected among source points i.e. the channels through which information are transported and necessary to maintain health. In, “Ayurveda and Modern Western Medicine”, Swami K.K.S Jyothimayananda, Italy described about the importance of Yoga and Ayurveda in acquiring health and happiness. Vaidya Atreya Smith, Director, European Institute of Vedic studies, France, discussed about the role of food for nourishment in “Nourishment according to Ayurveda” (Antonio Morandi *et.al.*, 2010). It has been seen that in the 21st century the main causes of mortality are related to stress, poor nutrition and lifestyle. In 2021 top global cause of death were associated with Cardiovascular and Respiratory (COVID-19, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, lower respiratory infections) with COVID-19 emerging as the 2nd leading cause of death globally. So the causes of death can be categorised into Communicable, Non Communicable and injuries (W.H.O. Top Ten Causes of Death,2024). The western medicine or modern medicine focuses mainly on external factors but Ayurveda system treats a disease through analysing different constitutions, which in turn define the type of treatment. Western medicine is effective or efficient in acute conditions which need immediate care and medication not the root cause. But in Ayurveda treatment the health of the individual, the environment, the society are interconnected. It is the holistic system of medicine (Antonio Morandi *et.al.*, 2010,).

Modern Concept of Health

In ancient Greece the concept of health, the balance between person and environment, the unity of soul and body, and the natural origin of disease was the backbone of perception of health. In the middle age health perception was influenced by the religion and the Church. During Industrial Revolution it became economic category.

WHO stated (1948) “health is a complete physical, mental, and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity.” This states that social welfare is also an important part of overall health, as social environment and living conditions are closely associated to the state of health. Later the definition of health has been amended where the fourth dimension - spiritual health was considered. All modern concepts of health now visualize health in the concept of wholeness which is more than the absence of diseases. The first International Conference on health promotion was held in Ottawa, Canada in 1986. The Ottawa Charter of this conference relates health in the context of everyday life and environment, where the people live and work. (Anna Lydia Savalastog *et.al.*,2017 PMC). In USSR, Alma Ata in 1978 at the International Conference on Primary Healthcare one of its declarations was that Health is an integral part of development, and its attainment requires promotive,

preventive, curative and rehabilitative services. The 36th World Health assembly of the WHO, meeting 1983 adopted

“The Global strategy for Health for All by the year 2000” (Madhabendra Pal,1988).

Modern Medicine

Modern medicine is mostly palliative which reduces the severity of pain or a disease without removing the root cause. In developed Countries the demand of preventive medicine has increased with the increasing well-being and longer lifespans, which can improve health through modern technologies. Medicine has been predicted to cure all types of diseases throughout the human history but it never come true. In the beginning of the 19th century the average life expectancy was as low as 40 years (Greene,2001, as cited in *Medicine of the future: How and who is going to treat us?* The life expectancy for the world has reached 72.6 years by 2020 but the mental health claims has increased over 100 percent over last ten years (Gunawan *et.al.*,2020 as cited in *Medicine of the future: How and who is going to treat us?*). With the breakthroughs in genetics and bioinformatics and the availability of technology, medicine is shifting from healthy lifestyle recommendations to highly accurate diagnostic tests, such as DNA tests. COVID – 19 Pandemic has also influenced the development of technology in the field of medicine. Robots are now used in taking care of patients, to disinfect spaces. AI can predict the spread of a virus in public place (*Medicine of the future: How and who is going to treat us?* (Julia Kulkova *et.al.*,2023). Modern medicine is the healthcare system which applies the evidence based practices and advanced technologies to diagnose, treat and prevent diseases with medications, surgeries, and therapies.

“To Err is Human” the seminal report published by the Institute of Medicine in U.S in 1999 estimated 98000 deaths in hospitals per year due to medical errors.

In 19th and 20th centuries the world has seen breakthroughs occurring in infection control. The percentage of death due to infection fallen to less than 4 percent by the end of 20th century from 30 percent at the end of 19th century. Researches are going on to move medical science forward. Targeted cancer therapy, HIV treatment, Stem cell therapy, Gene therapy, Robotics are now the new advancements in 21st centuries medical science (What is modern medicine? MNT editorial team, 2023).

In the modern era the concept of diet and medicine are gaining recognition as deeply interconnected. The modern diets are suggested according to the different parameters like Body Mass Index, genetic predisposition, and food and Drug intolerance of an individual patient. With the progress in modern medicine there are many challenges which again remind us about Ayurveda. Urbanization, digital information noise which are the sources of chronic stress can be the challenge for mental and physiological long –term health (Kulkova *et.al.*,2023).

Modern medicine focuses on alleviating symptoms, overlooking underlying imbalances which can't heal the root cause. In the developing and underdeveloped countries to the people of rural areas or underserved areas, cost of diagnostics and treatment is the main issue which make the treatment unreachable to them. Now a day's excessive use of antibiotics has led drug resistance to rise which in turn diminish antimicrobial efficacy. After Covid -19 Pandemic the stress, anxiety, depression and chronic stress has increased in such a way which is challenging the current healthcare model. Increased level of pollution is the reason for increased risk of respiratory problem, cardiovascular diseases, lung cancer, neurological disorder, reproductive health. So in this context there have to be more effective way in modern medicine to address these increasing challenges. Here the Indian Knowledge system works in many field and act as light of hope to face and cope up or minimise these challenges.

Ayurvedic Approach to Health and Medicine

The Ayurvedic concept appeared between 2500 and 500 BC in India (V.Subhose *et.al.*,2005). According to Ayurveda “Svasthya” is the optimal health which is achieved through the balance between structural and physiological factors, metabolic and excretory process, body tissues, senses, mind. Dasavidha pariksha i.e tenfold assessment where ten factors namely dusya (Body tissue), desa (residing location), Bala (physical strength), kala (Season), agni (digestive and metabolic process), prakriti (genetic and phenetic constitution), vaya (age), sattva (mental strength), satmya (habituation) and ahara (food) are used to determine the state of health. Health and diseases are dependent on three factors likely Ahara (diet), vihara (lifestyle) and ousadha (Drug and therapies). According to Ayurveda Ahara is considered most important for healthy life, and our six psychological expressions

–lust, anger, greed, desire, attachment and ego are linked with disease manifestation. These psychological states again are closely linked with foods. In case of disease management, pathya-wholesome food is very important. Pomegranate, butter milk, amla are treated as good pathya in management of anemia. Curd is treated as unwholesome-Apathya in most dosa imbalanced condition. Ayurveda has its own principle, method and practices which are very much different from biomedicine and modern nutrition concept (Unnikrishnan and Venkatasubramanniam,2016). In Ayurveda the treatment is aimed at prevention of diseases and cure of manifested diseases through proper food, lifestyle and oushadha. Three basic humors of human body: Vatadosha, Pittadosha, Kaphadosha which are collectively called as Tridoshas are believed to be formed from five elements Vayu (Air), Jala (Water), Akash (Space), Prithvi (Earth) and Teja (agni) referred to as Panchamahabhoota. If the balance between

Tridosha is lost, then different complication arises and to normalize body functions varied techniques including advice on food and activity, herbal preparations, purification techniques, surgical methods are suggested.

- **Ahara** (food): Ayurveda emphasizes basic dietary guidelines which are essential for well-being or health.

These guidelines are:

1. Kale bhojana- Intake of food in time
2. Satmya Bhojana- Food intake as per suitability
3. Hita Bhojana- as per the prakrithi
4. Suchi Bhojana- proper hygiene
5. Usna Bhojana- warm food
6. Laghu Bhojana- Easy to digest
7. Swad-rasa yukta Bhojana- food with six taste components
8. Nati druta vilambita- ingested calmly, neither too slow nor too fast
9. Snatah- After bathing
10. Kshudvan- food should be taken when there is sufficient hunger
11. Dhauta-pada-kara-anana- washing of hand, feet, face before taking food
12. Moun- Silently

Food intake method

Practice of eating should be mindful, which include; chewing food thoroughly, eating in a calm and peaceful environment, eating periodically and taking light meal at night (Ayurveda based diet & lifestyle guidelines for prevention and management of skin Diseases, ministry of Ayush)

Breakfast is suggested as wholesome and light, tailored according to individual's dosha. Balanced diet should be consumed. Virudhahara is also pivotal in the pathogenesis of disease. Acharya Charaka defined this Virudhahara as the diet which interrupts the metabolism process and inhibits tissue formation.

- **Vihara** (Lifestyle): Ayurveda describes lifestyle measures to maintain health and longevity. Lifestyle which is the characteristic of different behaviours that make sense to other and oneself in a given time and place including social relations consumption and entertainment.

Two practices which are important for health are as follows:

- **Dinacharya:** This is the daily regimen which starts with the predawn awakening i.e. waking in Brahma Muhurtya (1.5 hours before sunrise) invigorates the body, mind, setting a positive tone for the day. Simple practices like prayer, meditation and viewing the rising sun nurture tranquillity and prepares the individual for the day's challenge. Cleansing the body, including tongue scraping, oil pulling, eye washing removes toxic substances and refreshes the body (Ministry of Ayush).
- **Ritucharya:** This is the seasonal routine where it is believed that each season affects the doshas in unique ways. Spring to Winter rituals starts in detoxifying in spring to nourishing in winter. In spring bitter, hot, and astringent diet are advised and salty, sour and sweet food should be avoided.

In Summer aggravation of pitta occurs due to hot climate and for that reason hot, spicy, sour, salty diet should be avoided. In rainy season s due to the chance of aggravation of vata, vata-samaka sweet, sour, salty foods and drinks are preferred.

Disease Management and Treatments

In Ayurveda in case of disease management astasthan pariksha or 8-point diagnosis which includes nadi pariksha, mutra pariksha, mala pariksha, jihva pariksha, sabda pariksha, netra pariksha, twacha pariksha, akriti pariksha are done. This diagnosis involves assessment of doshic imbalance, understanding the patient's prakriti and life style, diet and environmental influence.

Charaka Samhita describes about four component of disease management scheme which include the physician, drug, patient and the attendant. Both Charaka Samhita and Susruta Samhita emphasizes illness management as four-part procedure which includes Shodan (cleansing), Shaman (palliation), Rasayan (rejuvenation) and Satwajaya (mental nurturing and spiritual healing).

India still need to overcome the issues of malnutrition and communicable diseases. But now the country is witnessing the rising burden of Non Communicable disease caused by lifestyle and environmental factors (Mudit Handa,2024).

Lifestyle based Diseases

Diseases which are non-communicable but are the effect of our life style known as lifestyle diseases. The type of food we eat, duration of sleep, how much we exercise, methods of handling of stress determine these types of diseases. According to the data of WHO (2016) 40.5 million people died of this Non communicable disease (NCD) and 2022 statistics of WHO revealed that NCD's killed 43 million people in the year 2021. The agenda (2030) for sustainable development recognizes NCDs as a major challenge for sustainable development (WHO, Non Communicable Disease, 2024). Recent research states that the main cause of illness, disability and death in India includes hypertension, cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes, lung and renal diseases, trauma, stroke, mental diseases. So its high time to take step to prevent and control these risk factors.

Herbal based Nutraceuticals

The Modern medicine does effective treatments but questionable in terms of long term management, addressing the root cause of unhealthy lifestyle and minimizing side effects. So the promising way to address these life style diseases is herbal based nutraceuticals. These are derived from plants which have been traditionally used in Ayurveda and other traditional system of medicine in India. In India Ayurvedic medicine market is approx. INR 50 billion in 2023. The bioactive compounds found in herbs are used for the management of lifestyle diseases.

Nutraceuticals Used in Lifestyle Disease Management

Herb/Medicinal Plant	Major compound	Potential Health Benefits
Turmeric (<i>Curcuma longa</i>)	curcumin	Anti-inflammatory; Anticancer; Antioxidant
Cinnamon (<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i>)	Cinnamaldehyde	Antioxidant, Insulin sensitizer, Reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease, diabetes.
Ashwagandha (<i>Withania somnifera</i>)	Withanolides	Reduces anxiety, stress and improve sleep, boost immunity
Aloe vera (<i>Aloe barbadensis miller</i>)	Polysaccharides, amino acid, vitamins, minerals	Antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory. Used in eczema, psoriasis, sun burn, treat digestive problems
Neem (<i>Azadiracta indica</i>)	Azadirachtin	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer
Indian Gooseberry (<i>Emblica officinalis</i>)	Vitamin C, Gallic acid, ellagic acid, quercetin	Immunity booster, improves digestion, promotes healthy skin, antioxidant
Green tea (<i>Camellia sinensis</i>)	polyphenols	Antioxidant, anti- inflammatory
Garlic (<i>Allium sativum</i>)	Allicin, Ajoene	Immunity booster, cardioprotective, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
Flaxseeds (<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>)	Omega 3 fatty acid, protein, fiber	Antibacterial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory

In Indian population there is a prevalence of lifestyle diseases and a significant portion of Indian population actively use herbal based nutraceuticals for lifestyle disease management. But these nutraceuticals can interact with other medications so proper care should be taken (Anuradha Singh,2024).

A Healthy Lifestyle needs a pure psychological and innate control over the physical and sensory activities. When these initiation, control and coordination are disturbed it leads to lifestyle disorder. It is called as 'Prajnapardha' in Ayurveda and it one of the three basic causes of any disease. Ayurveda offers various regimen to manage lifestyle disease. These regimens are Dinacharya, Ritucharya, Panchakarma (five detoxification), and Rasayana (rejuvenation) therapies. Sadvrita the ideal routine and Achara Rasayana (the code of conduct) are utmost important to maintain happy and healthy life (H.M Chandola,2012). Ahara and Vihara play a crucial role in our life. Ayurveda focuses more on Ahara or diet for healthy life but irregular timing, overfeeding, incompatible diet can aggravate three doshas- Vata which produces constipation, colic pain, dryness of mouth, fainting, giddiness; Pitta which causes fever, diarrhoea, thirst, intoxication, internal burning sensation; Kapha which causes vomiting, indigestion, laziness (Pooja Hui,2023).

Cardiovascular Disease

Sushruta in a section Kaya Chikitsa Tantra described treatment of heart diseases. This hridroga were reported to dysfunction of vayu (circulation) especially prana (air exchange) and vana vayu (omni present air). Pranvayu seemed to be associated with blood cleansing and the aadan of rasa-rakta complex, valve closure and generating praspand. Defective way of pranvayu and udayanvayu could result in enlargement of heart. In arthritis valve or mandala sandhis could become affected. The rhythmicity is controlled by vyanavayu. The Avalambaka kapha considered to be associated with pericardial effusion, pleural effusion and pulmonary edema (Indian Heart Journal,2021). Persons with poor sleeping habits are found to have high risk of high blood pressure, stroke, irregular heartbeats. In the era of lifestyle disorder Ayurveda could be the light of hope to maintain a healthy life (Pooja Hui,2023).

Arthritis

Most common types of arthritis are osteoarthritis and Rheumatoid arthritis. In India vata dosha is a common colloquial term used to denote Rheumatism primarily affecting joints. In the classic texts different forms of arthritis along with nervous system disorders are mentioned. Vata dosha plays crucial role in the causation of arthritis. Joints and soft tissues are affected by "ama" produced in the gut due to weakened agni or equilibrium loss of doshas resulting in inflammatory and obstructive processes. Ayurveda formulations targets joints, gut and immune systems. Thousands of years later modern medicine found immune related link between certain gut disorders and inflammatory arthritis. In ayurvedic treatment of arthritis rasayana properties of medicinal herbs and minerals are used which aims to increase the body's resistance to disease, delay aging and promote body strength. One rasayana plant is Withania somnifera used as anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic. In Charaka Samhita different antiarthritic medicinal plant are mentioned –Ricinus communis (castor oil) and Guggul (Extracts). Guggul extract ofent contain bhsama or ash of mineral such as gold, silver, copper, mercury, sulphur, lead, zinc. Gold in ayurvedic ash form has been used since ancient times and modern medicine has also discovered its use as disease-modifying anti rheumatic drug (DMARD). Snehana (oleation) and swedana (sweating, heating) are two basic process for the treatment of arthritis. Oil preparations are administered orally. All this aims to balance tridoshas. Panchakarma treatments are used to cure dosha imbalance. Dietary restriction and physical exercises and yoga are suggested at appropriate stages of recovery. Pain relief is done by local application of plant extracts. To alleviate vata, removing subcutaneous fat, reducing pain and fatigue Ayurvedic massage is very popular now. During massage Ayurvedic pressure points are used to stimulate nervous system and internal organs. Yoga has been described as the best way for mental and physical fitness.

In modern medicine in the treatment of Rheumatoid arthritis for immediate pain relief analgesic and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are suggested which may cause deleterious effects in gastrointestinal, renal and cardiovascular systems. Steroids are also used as anti-inflammatory agents. DMARD are currently intended to controlling disease process its activity and progression. They act slowly but nullifies the requirements of analgesics, NSAIDs or steroids (Arvind Chopra *et.al.*,2010).

Surgical Principals in Sushruta Samhita

The branch of medical science which deals with diagnostics and management of wounds, removal of any substance and handling of surgical instruments in general, together with the diagnosis and treatment of ulcers referred as Shalya Tantra (Surgery). Sushruta Samhita contains detailed description of teaching and practice of ancient surgeon Sushruta. In Poorva Karma Sushruta directs the surgeon to be prepared with the essential things related with surgery such as surgical instruments, alkali, fire, probe, horns, gourd, cotton, thread, honey, milk, oil, decoctions, cold water, hot water, paste (kalka) etc. It proves that the simple things required for surgery Sushruta was aware of. For aseptic condition fumigation which is referred as Dhoopana in Charaka and Shusruta Samhita are prescribed. Before surgical operations patients should be kept on empty stomach is also mentioned. Shusruta describes eight types of surgical act like Chedana (Incising), Bhedya (Excising), Iekhya (Scraping), Vyadana (probing), Eshana (Extracting), Visravaya (Draining secreting fluids), Seevya (Suturing). In the treatment of Haemorrhoids and other Anorectal diseases four types of treatments were suggested and the surgery indicated as last option. In case of intestinal perforation (Chidrodara) the same is followed in modern improved surgery. In case of Surgical instrument, it has been mentioned that tempering should be done with alkali, water or oil to keep instruments in good condition. Sushruta clearly mentioned the importance of prognosis to the patient and patient's relatives before doing surgery which are relevant to this present era too. The detailed description of different instruments, pre and post-operative preparations, sterilisation process all are proof of ethical surgical practices in Ayurveda times or Sushruta times. Many modifications of the treatment procedures or principles were also welcomed at that era. Shusruta was the first to perform plastic surgery (Kembhavi SA, *et.al.*, 2022).

Bridging Tradition and modernity

Potential of ayurvedic formulations is vast. Ayurveda offers a large scope for research and development. In case of lifestyle disease like diabetes, obesity the challenge of antibiotic resistance and mental health in modern medicine could be addressed by Ayurvedic formulations. The rising trend of personalised medicine in Modern medicine aligns the Ayurvedic prakriti based treatment (Umapati CB *et.al.*, 2025). Charaka Samhita encourages contemporary research in Ayurveda. The role of Gut health which is called Agni in Ayurveda along with many herbal formulations and principles are now increasingly supported by modern scientific studies. The integration of Charaka Samhita into modern medicine provides solutions to emerging challenge of global health like lifestyle disorder, stress and drug resistance (Umapati CB *et.al.*, 2025).

Conclusion

Ayurveda has proven its role and importance in this era of modern medicine. Unhealthy lifestyle i.e. improper diet, smoking, lack of exercise, stress, are the major contributors to lifestyle disorder such as high blood pressure, cholesterol, diabetes, obesity, stroke, heart attack, cancer, chronic bronchitis, renal failure, emphysema, depression etc. The history of Indian Traditional medicine system shows the rich contribution of different surgeon and physicians. Here we have seen that Ayurveda is a treasure trove of ancient wisdom. Through research in Ayurveda the gap between ancient traditions and modern science can be bridged. Ayurvedic treatments pave the way for its integration into main stream healthcare systems worldwide. Several lifestyle conditions are nearly impossible to treat through modern medicine but Ayurveda may be able to treat and prevent these illnesses in humans. In few cases heavy metal was found in Ayurvedic medicines. So further research is crucial to establish the efficacy, safety of Ayurvedic formulations or nutraceuticals and also for the optimal dosages for specific condition. Sushruta's remarkable contributions to surgery and medicine laid a foundation stone that continues to influence modern practice. His unparalleled skill of rhinoplasty, cataract surgery and bone settings revolutionized medical practices. With the rising global interest in sustainable healthcare solutions Ayurvedic formulations or Ayurveda can be the beacon or testament in making of Vikshit Bharat.

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